

Supplementary Figures S1-S5

Figure S1 Linkage disequilibrium decay plot. Linkage disequilibrium (LD), measured as r^2 , between pairs of single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) loci is plotted against the genetic distance (kb). SNPs located within 5 kb showed high LD ($r^2 = 0.997$). The left graph magnifies the boxed region in the right graph.

Figure S2 Phenotyping of rice seed hull color. We first trimmed only the image of seeds. Next, we extracted the representative color of the seeds using principal component analysis. Finally, we converted RGB values of representative seed hull color to y-axis values of CIE XYZ color space. Y-axis values of CIE XYZ color space is indicated by red color.

Figure S3 Relationships between rice seed hull color phenotypes and the genotypes of the three major quantitative trait loci (QTLs). Boxplots showing the phenotypic values of

recombinant inbred lines (RILs) (y-axis) in relation to their genotypes at the three major QTLs (x-axis). The horizontal line inside each box represents median value. Box range is the first and third quartile. The whisker extends to last datum less than the third quartile + $1.5 \times$ interquartile range (IQR) and the first datum greater than the first quartile – $1.5 \times$ IQR. (a) The phenotypic values of RILs separately shown for Hitomebore or Kaluheenati genotypes at the SNP on chr04:23121877. (b) The phenotypic values of RILs separately shown for Hitomebore or Kaluheenati genotypes at the SNP on chr04:33353823. (c) The phenotypic values of RILs separately shown for Hitomebore or Kaluheenati genotypes at the SNP on chr09:6953870.

Figure S4 Relationships between phenotypic values and genotypes of the two epistatic single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) as identified by RIL-StEp and quantitative trait loci (QTL) identified by genome-wide association study for seed hull color. A boxplot showing the phenotypic values of recombinant inbred lines with different combinations of genotypes at SNPs on chr01:30449415, chr03:2749620. The horizontal line inside each box represents

median value. Box range is the first and third quartile. The whisker extends to last datum less than the third quartile + 1.5*interquartile range (IQR) and the first datum greater than the first quartile – 1.5*IQR. Top boxplot considered the epistasis effect of chr04:23034736 and chr04:32487760. Bottom boxplot considered the QTL effect of chr09:6953870. The x-axis shows the combinations of genotypes. The y-axis shows phenotypic values.

Figure S5A DNA sequence alignment of the variant part of the *BH4* gene. Top: a simplified scheme of *BH4* gene structure and the region shown in the alignment. Coding regions are indicated by orange color. Bottom: aligned genome sequences of *BH4* for Hitomebore, Kaluheenati, and Nipponbare (reference genome). Hitomebore and Nipponbare sequences have a 22-bp deletion in the coding region of *BH4*. All alignment results are in Zenodo ([10.5281/zenodo.3688821](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3688821)).

CDS

<i>Phr1</i> Hitomebore	1952	CCGTGCGGGTGGCCGTGACGAGGCCAGGGCGTCGAGGAG	1991
<i>Phr1</i> Nipponbare	1952	CCGTGCGGGTGGCCGTGACGAGGCCAGGGCGTCGAGGAG	1991
<i>Phr1</i> Kaluheenati	1961	CCGTGCGGGTGGCCGTGACGAGGCCAGGGCGTCGAGGAG	2000
		CCGTGCGGGTGGCCGTGACGAGGCCAGGGCGTCGAGGAG	
<i>Phr1</i> Hitomebore	1992	CCGCGAGGAGAAGGAGGAGGAGGAGGAGGT	2021
<i>Phr1</i> Nipponbare	1992	CCGCGAGGAGAAGGAGGAGGAGGAGGAGGT	2021
<i>Phr1</i> Kaluheenati	2001	CCGCGAGGAGAAGGAGGAGGAGGAGGAGGTGCTCGTCATC	2040
		CCGCGAGGAGAAGGAGGAGGAGGAGGAGGTGCTCGTCATC	
<i>Phr1</i> Hitomebore	2022	-----CGAGATCCCCGACCACTCCACGTACGTCAAGT	2053
<i>Phr1</i> Nipponbare	2022	-----CGAGATCCCCGACCACTCCACGTACGTCAAGT	2053
<i>Phr1</i> Kaluheenati	2041	GAGGGGATCGAGATCCCCGACCACTCCACGTACGTCAAGT	2080
		GAGGGGATCGAGATCCCCGACCACTCCACGTACGTCAAGT	
<i>Phr1</i> Hitomebore	2054	TCGACGTGTTTCGTGAACGCGCCCGAGAGCGGGGACGGCGC	2093
<i>Phr1</i> Nipponbare	2054	TCGACGTGTTTCGTGAACGCGCCCGAGAGCGGGGACGGCGC	2093
<i>Phr1</i> Kaluheenati	2081	TCGACGTGTTTCGTGAACGCGCCCGAGAGCGGGGACGGCGC	2120
		TCGACGTGTTTCGTGAACGCGCCCGAGAGCGGGGACGGCGC	
<i>Phr1</i> Hitomebore	2094	GGCGACGTGCGCGGCGACGTGCGCCGGCAGCGTCGCGCTG	2133
<i>Phr1</i> Nipponbare	2094	GGCGACGTGCGCGGCGACGTGCGCCGGCAGCGTCGCGCTG	2133
<i>Phr1</i> Kaluheenati	2121	GGCGACGTGCGCGGCGACGTGCGCCGGCAGCGTCGCGCTG	2160
		GGCGACGTGCGCGGCGACGTGCGCCGGCAGCGTCGCGCTG	
<i>Phr1</i> Hitomebore	2134	GCGCCGCACGGGATCCACCGCGAGGGGCAGCTGTCGCCGA	2173
<i>Phr1</i> Nipponbare	2134	GCGCCGCACGGGATCCACCGCGAGGGGCAGCTGTCGCCGA	2173
<i>Phr1</i> Kaluheenati	2161	GCGCCGCACGGGATCCACCGCGAGGGGCAGCTGTCGCCGA	2200
		GCGCCGCACGGGATCCACCGCGAGGGGCAGCTGTCGCCGA	

Figure S5B DNA sequence alignment of the variant part in the *Phr1* gene. Top: a simplified scheme of *Phr1* gene structure and the region shown in the alignment. Coding regions are indicated by orange color. Bottom: aligned genome sequences of *Phr1* for Hitomebore, Kaluheenati, and Nipponbare (reference genome). Hitomebore and Nipponbare have an 18-bp deletion in the coding region of *Phr1*. All alignment results are in Zenodo ([10.5281/zenodo.3688821](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3688821)).

Figure S5C DNA sequence alignment of the variant part in the *IBF1* gene. Top: a simplified scheme of *IBF1* gene structure and the region shown in the alignment. Coding region is indicated by orange color. Bottom: aligned genome sequences of *IBF1* for Hitomebore, Kaluheenati, and Nipponbare (reference genome). Kaluheenati has a 19-bp deletion and one genetic variant in *IBF1*. All alignment results are in Zenodo ([10.5281/zenodo.3688821](https://zenodo.org/record/3688821)).